

ISic1421

I.Sicily inscription 1421

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Kasmenai

Place of origin (modern)

near Chiaramonte Gulfi

Provenance

Monte Casale

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50114

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332710

1. [Κ]αλικράτε^ς ²⁶Καλλικράτης²⁶ καλός:ο,ιο[...].ίπου
νόθος, Αἴσα Νουνφί-
2. [ο⁻]νος τοκῆς *hoi*, κῆλαβον χό⁻ρε⁻[ν] *h[o]i ho⁻ς* μέ [λ] ξ,ιν ἄμεινο-
3. ν καὶ *ho⁻ς* ἄμ' εἶναι.
- 4.

Edition: PHI333360

1. Καλικράτε^ς καλός [ὀ] Κ [ρα(?)]σίπου καὶ Λο⁻σαις Ἀμουνφί-
2. ο⁻νος τοκῆς *hoi* κ' ἔλαβον χό⁻ρε⁻[ν] *hōi ho⁻ς* μνέ⁻μα μεῖν-
3. αι καὶ *ho⁻ς* ἄμ[α] εἶ[ν]αι.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644971

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PHI 332710

PHI 333360

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